

The Influence of Compensation on Human Resource Performance in the Environmental Services of South Halmaera District

Tineke Sumual¹, Sjeddie Watung², Shelty Sumual³, Jumrah Jamil^{4*}, Heidi Kristian Repi⁵

^{1,2,3,5}Manado University, ⁴STAI Al-Khairaat Halmahera Selatan

Corresponding Author: Jumrah Jamil jumrahjamil@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Compensation, HR Performance

Received : 22, October

Revised : 21, September

Accepted: 30, December

©2022 Sumual, Watung, Sumual, Jamil, Repi: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research intends to investigate and assess how compensation affects the performance of human resources in the Environmental Department of South Halmahera Regency. The method in writing this article is a quantitative research technique, namely building theory by testing the relationship between variables. These variables can be measured and explained as instruments with relevant statistical analysis that can be interpreted. The benefit the purpose of this essay is to ascertain how compensation affects the performance of human resources in the Environmental Department of South Halmahera Regency. The research results reveal that this can be achieved well if the human resources within the company/organization are handled by appropriate management of human resources. It was determined that whenever there was a rise in compensation, employee morale increased. Suggestions require adjustments to compensation to increase employee morale at the South Halmahera Regency Environmental Service, both now and in the future and it is hoped that in the future it will be further improved to achieve organizational goals.

INTRODUCTION

In carrying out its activities, a company will try to fulfill the objectives and work toward making the business more competitive maintain its survival. One important factor in efforts to improve a company is human resources. Companies must strive to improve their human resources effectively and efficiently. Human resources are the main asset and play a crucial part in a company's ability to survive in its efforts to achieve its goals. Company goals can be achieved well if the human resources within the company are handled by appropriate human resource management (Koopmans, et al. 2014).

Every individual from an organization has their interests and goals when joining an organization or company. For some employees, the hope of earning money is the only reason for working. As a result, a worker gains an appreciation for diligence and grows more devoted to the organization; as a result, the employer recognizes and compensates workers for their efforts. both directly and indirectly. Compensation is part of the reciprocal relationship between the organization and human resources. According to Wibowo (2007), employee compensation is all forms of payment or rewards given to employees and arises from their work and has two components: direct payments (in the form of wages, salaries, incentives, commissions and bonuses), and indirect payments (in the form of wages, salaries, incentives, commissions and bonuses). forms of financial benefits such as insurance and vacation pay paid by the company).

Employee compensation is something they get in exchange for the services they perform for the business. Each person working for an organization wants to be paid what they are worth. According to Hasibuan (2014), the goals of offering compensation include fostering cooperative relationships, performance improvement, factors such as government and labor union influence, employee stability, motivation, work satisfaction, and efficient procurement. Sedarmayanti (2011) said that A good compensation plan should be flexible enough to adjust to changing circumstances and capable of inspiring staff members. Compensation systems should satisfy employees' needs, ensure their fair treatment and reward their demonstration. When employees of the company are content with their pay, they will consistently perform their duties.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In writing this Journal Article, the researcher explored information from several previous studies as comparison material, both regarding existing advantages and disadvantages. Apart from that, researchers also dig up information from books, theses, theses and journals to obtain previously existing information about theories related to the title used to obtain a scientific theoretical basis:

1. Research conducted by Dr. E. Marno Nugroho MM, entitled: The Influence of Training, Motivation, Competency on Human Resource Performance. This research aims to describe the relationship between training, competency and self-actualization motivation on HR performance and to develop a model for improving optimal HR performance. The independent variables in the research are training,

competency and self-actualization motivation. The dependent variable is HR performance. And the intervening variable is competence. The population in the study were permanent employees at PDAM Tirta Kencana, Samarinda City. The sample was calculated using the Slovin formula and the result was 177 respondents. Data collection was carried out by observation, documentation, several previous journals, interviews, and questionnaires which were distributed directly. The Descriptive and statistical methods are used in analysis. The findings indicate that the training, competency and motivation variables have a positive effect on HR performance and training has an indirect effect on HR performance through the competency intervening variable.

2. Research conducted by Marta Nasrani Gee¹, et al, entitled: Compensation's Impact on Workers' Work Morale at the Telukdalam Subdistrict South Nias Regency Office. The purpose of this study is to ascertain how employee morale at the Telukdalam Subdistrict Office is impacted by compensation South Nias Regency. The method used is quantitative with simple linear regression analysis techniques, using questionnaire data distributed to 32 employees at the Telukdalam Subdistrict Office, South Nias Regency. The results of the research show that compensation has a positive and significant influence on employee work morale at the Telukdalam Subdistrict Office, South Nias Regency with a significant level of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a count $(6.388) > \text{table } (1.697)$, suggesting a positive and strong correlation between the compensation variable and work morale. employee at the Telukdalam Subdistrict Office, South Nias Regency. It was concluded that when there was an increase in compensation, employee morale increased. The suggestion is that there is a need to adjust compensation to increase employee morale at the Telukdalam Subdistrict Office, South Nias Regency, both now and in the future and it is hoped that in the future it will be further improved to achieve organizational goals.
3. Research conducted by Muhammad Yuniyanto, et al, entitled: The Influence of Compensation and HR Competency on the Performance of Sumenep Employees with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable (Study at the District Public Works and Spatial Planning Service). The research results show that: 1) Compensation for employee performance has a positive and 2) HR competency has a positive and significant impact on employee performance, as demonstrated by the Original Sample value of 0.283 the Original Sample value of 0.448. 3) Work motivation compensation has a positive and significant effect as evidenced by the Original Sample value of 0.385. 4) HR competency has a positive and significant effect on work motivation as evidenced by the Original Sample value of 0.458. 5) Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance as evidenced by the Original Sample value of 0.303. 6) Compensation for The Original Sample value of 0.116 indicates a positive and significant effect of work motivation on employee performance 7) HR competency on worker performance

influenced by motivation at work has a noteworthy favorable impact, as shown by the 0.139 Original Sample value.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this research is quantitative which is based on calculating numbers and statistics. This research is a causal influence that exists between the dependent and independent variables. Kasiram in Sujarweni (2014:39), "Quantitative research methods are a process of discovering knowledge that uses data in the form of numbers as a tool for analyzing information about what you want to know".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Nature of Compensation

1. Definition of Compensation

Employees receive compensation in lieu of providing the company with their services. One of the application functions of human resource management (HRM) is compensation, which is associated with all forms of individual rewards for completing tasks related to the organization (Rivai, 2009: 741). According to Handoko (1993:155), pay is significant for employees as people since it shows the extent of their contributions to the neighborhood, their families, and themselves.

According to Sedarmayanti (2011), employee compensation is all forms of payment or gifts given to employees and arises from their work and has two components, namely direct payments (wages, salaries, incentives, commissions and bonuses), and indirect payments (Cash and insurance). vacation funded by the company). Pratama According to et al. (2015), compensation is everything received by employees as remuneration for the company's services to employees in the form of salaries, facilities and so on which can be valued in money and is permanent. Apart from that, providing compensation is a strategic function of human resources.

Awards are another name for compensation, which is any kind of recognition given to staff members in exchange for their contributions to the company (Panggabean, 2002: 181). Compensation is a benefit or prize given to employees who, through their labor, have helped achieve their objectives (Nawawi, 2001:316). Apart from that, in Hasibuan's book (2002:91) there are several definitions of compensation from several figures, namely:

- a. According to Werther and Davis, compensation is what a worker receives in return for the work he provides. Both hourly wages and periodic wages are designed and managed by the personnel department.
- b. According to Sikula, compensation is anything that is constituted or considered as remuneration or equivalent.

2. Purpose of Compensation

For organizations or companies, compensation has an important meaning because compensation reflects the organization's efforts to maintain

and improve the welfare of its employees. So, providing compensation helps launch the organization's strategy because compensation influences job satisfaction and performance. As stated by Hasibuan (2014), the goals of offering compensation include:

- a. Collaborative ties, through the provision of remuneration creates a formal cooperative relationship between the employer and workers. Workers perform their duties effectively, and business executives must make payments compensation.
- b. Job satisfaction, through providing employee compensation, is expected to fulfill their egoistic demands to feel fulfilled in their work and their physical and social standing.
- c. If a sizable enough compensation plan is in place, procurement is effective. and runs well then it will be simpler for entrepreneurs to find qualified workers.
- d. Motivation, managers will find it easy to motivate their subordinates if the remuneration provided is large enough.
- e. Employee stability, through compensation provided by the company with Because employee turnover is comparatively low, fair and appropriate principles and competitive external consistency are more likely to ensure employee stability.
- f. Discipline, employees will be aware of and obey existing regulations within the company by considering the compensation or remuneration they will receive from the company, so employee discipline will be better.
- g. The influence labor Employees can concentrate on their work and unions can be avoided if there is a good compensation plan in place.
- h. The influence of the government, if the compensation plan is subject to relevant labor laws (like minimum wage restrictions) that have been set then government intervention can be avoided.

3. Compensation Function

According to Samsudin (2010), the role that compensation plays is:

- a. Effective use of human resources: This feature demonstrates how rewarding exceptional workers will motivate them to produce better work.
- b. Employing people resources more effectively and efficiently: Providing compensation to employees implies that the organization will use employee energy effectively and efficiently.
- c. Encouraging economic stability and growth: Pay structures support both organizational stability and economic expansion in general.

4. Regulations Concerning Compensation

The rights of workers or laborers who are received and expressed in the form of money as compensation from entrepreneurs or employers to workers or laborers are defined as salary or wages under Law No. 13 of 2003 concerning Employment. These rights are determined and paid in accordance with a work agreement, agreement, or statutory regulations, including benefits for workers

or laborers and their families for work or services that have been or will be performed, namely:

1. Paragraph (1) of Article 88 states that "Every worker or laborer has the right to earn an income that fulfills a decent living for humanity".
2. The following is stated in Article 89 Paragraph 1: "Minimum wages comprise (1) Minimum wages based on provincial, district, or city areas (2) Sector-specific minimum wages in provincial, district, or urban areas".
3. The following is stated in Article 90 Paragraph 1: "Employers are prohibited from paying wages lower than the minimum wage as intended in Article 89".
4. Article 90 Paragraph (2) contains: "Entrepreneurs who are unable to pay the minimum wage as intended in article 89 may be subject to suspension".
5. Article 92 Paragraph (1) contains: "Employers prepare the structure and scale of wages by taking into account class, position, length of service, education and compensation".
6. Article 92 Paragraph (2) contains: "Employers carry out periodic wage reviews by paying attention to the company's productivity".
7. Article 94 contains: "In the wage component consisting of basic wages and fixed allowances, the amount of basic wages is at least 75% of the total basic wages and fixed allowances".

5. Factors Affecting Compensation

According to Mangkunegara (2009), six factors influence policies in providing compensation, namely:

- a. Government Factors: Government factors related to Government rules governing minimum wage requirements, income taxes, the cost of raw materials, freight or transportation expenses, inflation, and devaluation all have a significant impact on how much employers pay their employees. policies.
- b. A combined offer from the employer and the workers: Policies in determining compensation can also be influenced when bargaining occurs regarding the amount of wages that must be given by the company to its employees. This is mainly done by companies in recruiting employees who have expertise in certain fields that are needed in the company.
- c. Employee Cost of Living Standards: Compensation policies need to consider the employee's minimum cost of living standards. Employees' basic needs must be met. If the basic needs of employees and their families are met, employees will feel safe. Fulfilling employees' Employees who feel secure and have their basic needs met will be more motivated to work toward organizational objectives.
- d. Comparative Measures of Wages: Policies in determining compensation are also influenced by the size of the company, the employee's education level, and the employee's length of service.

- e. Demand and Supply: It is necessary to consider the level of supply and market demand in determining employee compensation policies.
- f. Ability to Pay: Determining employee compensation policies needs to be based on the company's ability to pay employees' wages. This means, do not determine compensation policies beyond the limits of the company's existing capabilities.

6. Compensation Indicator

There are two indicators proposed by Chun Hsi and Setyabudi (2008), namely:

- a. Financial compensation, which consists of:
 - 1. Salary: Salary is remuneration in the form of money that an employee receives as a consequence of his position as an employee who contributes energy and thoughts in achieving company goals or it can also be said to be a fixed payment that a person receives from membership in a company.
 - 2. Bonuses: A bonus is a lump sum payment awarded for achieving performance goals or, in the event that the goal is surpassed, monetary compensation for the completed work. An employee who is worth more to the company than their regular salary may also receive a bonus. Bonuses can also be given out as compensation for meeting predetermined objectives set by the business or for demonstrating loyalty to it.
 - 3. Incentives: Incentives are direct rewards given to workers whose performance surpasses predetermined benchmarks. Beyond wages and salaries, which are considered fixed compensation, incentives are another type of direct wages. These are typically referred to as performance-based compensation (pay for performance plan). Rewards known as incentives are assigned to members of a group based on how differently they complete their tasks. It's intended to provide

- b. Non-Financial Compensation

This is additional compensation given based on company policy to all employees to improve employee welfare. For example, overtime, insurance, holiday allowances, pensions, sick leave and maternity leave, while facilities include housing, moving costs and vehicles.

B. Human Resources Performance

1. Understanding HR Performance

According to Simamora (2017: 16) HR performance is work performance or work results, both quality and quantity, achieved by Over time, HR has fulfilled their assigned responsibilities in carrying out their work duties. To improve the quality of its products, a company needs employees as its workforce. Considering that employees are an important asset for the company, many things need to be considered regarding improving their performance.

Employee performance, Maryoto (2000:91) claims that is the result of labor finished over a predetermined amount of time. in comparison to a range of options, such as mutually agreed-upon standards, targets, or criteria. The

indicators include the amount and quality of work produced by workers as well as their input into the business. Per Soelaiman (2007:279), Sherman and Ghomes state that "Job performance is the amount of successful full role achievement".

According to Sulaiman in his book *Performance Management* (2007:279) provides an understanding of performance as something that is done and produced in the form of products or services, in a certain period and at a certain size by a person or group of people through their skills, abilities, knowledge and experience. He also explained (2007:283) that employee performance is the level to which employees achieve job requirements.

Performance is the degree to which an employee completes the tasks that comprise their employment (Simamora, August 2006). Achievement is a measure of how well a worker satisfies job requirements. the documentation of outcomes attained while performing specific job duties or tasks activities within a given time frame, as evidenced by the method or style of working and the outcomes obtained, is the definition of performance. According to In August 2006, Byars and Rue's performance is the extent to which an individual completes the tasks that go along with their work. Performance is what shows how well a person satisfies the requirements of their job. These definitions demonstrate that performance is a combination of qualitative and quantitative outcomes.

2. Factors that Influence Performance

Mangkuprawira and Hubeis state (2013:155), these factors are as follows:

- a. Personal Factors: Personal factors include elements of knowledge, skills, abilities, self-confidence, environment and commitment possessed by each individual
- b. Leadership Factors: Leadership factors include aspects of the quality of managers and team leaders in providing encouragement, enthusiasm, direction and work support to employees
- c. Team Factor: Team factors include the quality of support and enthusiasm provided by colleagues in a team, trust in fellow team members, cohesiveness and closeness of team members.
- d. System Factors: System factors include work systems, work facilities and infrastructure provided by the organization, compensation and organizational procedures and the culture of performance within the company
- e. Contextual Factors: Contextual factors include pressure and alterations to the internal and external surroundings.

3. Individual Character with High Performance

The character traits of individuals with high performance according to Mangkunegara (in Widiarko, 2017: 15) are:

- a. Individuals enjoy working and facing modest difficulties
- b. People are not very satisfied. They often become dissatisfied if the work is too easy or too difficult.
- c. People prefer to hear specific feedback about how well their work is going.

- d. People often detest assignments if they don't yield the expected achievements
- e. People would rather take personal responsibility for the tasks they carry out
- f. When the work is finished, people are happy with the outcomes. by themselves
- g. Individuals lack rest, tend to be innovative and travel a lot.
People are constantly searching for new and challenging employment opportunities, trying to break away from their routines and the familiar.

4. Performance Indicators

According to Simamora (2017: 16), employee performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him.

In this research, it is an indicator of worker effectiveness determined by the opinion of Simamora (2017: 16), namely:

- a. Loyalty
- b. Spirit at work
- c. Leadership
- d. Cooperation
- e. Responsibility

Based on the above, it is hoped that there will be the ability of agency management to maintain compensation indicators that are carried out to increase employee morale such as salaries, incentives, allowances and facilities. This aim is to increase employee morale at the South Halmahera Regency Environmental Service, both now and in the future. The study's findings indicate that compensation has an impact on how well human resources perform at the Environmental Service, South Halmahera Regency, North Maluku Province.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing from the findings of the investigation and subsequent discourse, it can be inferred that company goals can be achieved well if the human resources within the company are handled by appropriate human resource management. As a result, a worker gains an appreciation for diligence and grows more devoted to the organization; as a result, the employer recognizes and compensates workers for their efforts both directly and indirectly.

Any payment or benefit given to employees as a result of their work is referred to as employee compensation. It consists of two parts: direct payments, which take the form of wages, salaries, commissions, incentives, and bonuses, and indirect payments, which take the form of monetary benefits provided by the employer, such as insurance and paid time off.

FURTHER RESEARCH

Research design is a research plan and procedure developed from determining assumptions, collecting data, and analyzing and interpreting it. This The goal of fundamental research, also known as basic research, is to contribute to the advancement of science. (Sekaran, 2006). If we put it further, this study uses a quantitative research design namely building theory by testing the relationship between variables. These variables can be measured and explained as instruments with relevant statistical analysis that can be interpreted. (Creswell, 2014).

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was made possible thanks to the help of many parties. For this reason, we would like to thank the lecturers in Human Resources Management and the International Journal of Advanced Social Sciences and Education (IJASSE), and the International Journal of Management Analytics (IJMA) who have provided the opportunity to publish their work, so that this article is deemed worthy of publication.

REFERENCES

- Dr. E. Marno Nugroho MM, dan Renjana Paradifa , 2020, Pengaruh Pelatihan, Motivasi, Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia. *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sains Indonesia (JRMSI)* Vol 11, No. 1, 2020 e-ISSN: 2301- 8313
- Handoko, T. Hani. 2012. *Manajemen Personalia dan Sumber Daya Manusia*, Yogyakarta: BPFPE.
- Hasibuan, Malayu S. P. 2014, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Edisi Revisi: Jakarta. Bumi Aksara.
- Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C.M., Hildebrandt, V.H., Vet, H.C.W., de, Beek, A. J. 2014. "Construct Validity of Individual Work Performance Questionnaire". *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*. Volume 56, Number 3.
- Marta Nasrani Gee1, Dkk, Pengaruh Kompensasi Terhadap Semangat Kerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Camat Telukdalam Kabupaten Nias Selatan, Pareto: *Jurnal Riset Manajemen dan Bisnis* ISSN:2622-9811 Vol. 6 No. 1 Februari 2021
- Muhammad Yuniyanto, Dkk, Pengaruh Kompensasi Dan Kompetensi SDM Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Sumenep Dengan Motivasi Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Pada Dinas Pekerjaan Umum Dan Penataan Ruang Kabupaten). *ournal of Management and Creative Business (JMCBUS)* Vol.1, No.4 Oktober 2023 e-ISSN: 2962-1119; p-ISSN: 2962-0856, Hal 55-74
- Nawawi, H. 2001. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta. Gadjamada University Press
- Panggabean, Mutiara S, 2002. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.
- Pratama Stefanus Andi, Moehammad Soe'loed Hakam, Gunawan Eko Nurtjahjono, 2015. Pengaruh Kompensasi terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (studi pada karyawan pt. asuransi jiwa sraya persero regional office malang). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)* Vol. 25
- Rivai, Veitzhal & Ella Jauvan. 2009. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan*. Jakarta. PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Rivai, Veitzhal. 2005. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta. PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.

Sumual, Watung, Sumual, Jamil, Repi

Sedarmayanti. 2011. Sumber Daya Manusia, Reformasi Birokrasi dan Manajemen Pegawai Negeri Sipil. Edisi Kelima. Bandung: CV Mandar Maju.

Simamora, Henry. 2004. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Yogyakarta. STIE YKPN

Wibowo. 2007. Manajemen Kinerja. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada